

Mankind DNA Preservation Project

It is estimated that the number of people that have been deceased from the beginning of time till the present is 100 billion.

The **Mankind DNA Preservation Project** aims at collecting the DNA of every person who has ever lived on Earth, within one century, and preserve them all in a laboratory for future usage.

The purpose of this project is to study and analyze the structure of every human DNA on Earth to better understand it.

© *Copyright*

Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
06/01/2021